

USE OF MODULES AND ACQUISITION OF MOST ESSENTIAL LEARNING COMPETENCIES: INPUT FOR SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT

MANILYN MAGLINAO PUPAN

manilyn.maglinao@deped.gov.ph

ORCID No. 0000-0001-9263-5123

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The main goal of this study was to determine if there is a significant relationship between the use of modules and the students' acquisition of the most essential learning competencies in Technology and Livelihood Education. This study made use of the descriptive-correlational design. The respondents consisted of 55 TLE teachers who served in the public schools in the Third District of Batangas. The questionnaire was completed using Google Forms by the respondents. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to analyze the responses of the teachers. The respondent perceived that the use of modules in the students' acquisition of the most essential learning competencies in the dimension of learning through thought process ($M=4.21$), through action ($M=4.35$) and through implementation ($M=4.32$) all interpreted "to high extent." As to the level of students acquisition of the most essential learning competencies, it is "highly acquired", ($M=4.01$). Also the finding revealed that there is significant relationship between the use of modules and acquisition of the most essential learning competencies in planning in terms of thought process ($r=.546$), action ($r=.355$) and implementation ($r=.623$). In management the use of modules is related to delivery ($r=.594$). The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the use of the modules and the students' acquisition of the most essential learning competencies is not accepted as supported by evidences. It is recommended that teachers may ensure that the students understand the goals, aims, purpose and the learning outcomes of the modules. They may make sure that modules are constructively aligned to most essential learning competencies.

Keywords: Modules, Most Essential Learning Competencies, Supplementary Materials Development